

1 **Multifunctionality debt in global drylands linked to past biome and climate**

2

3 **Running head:** Legacy effects on dryland multifunctionality

4

5 Jian-Sheng Ye^{1*}, Manuel Delgado-Baquerizo^{2,3}, Santiago Soliveres⁴ and Fernando T.
6 Maestre³

7

8 ¹State Key Laboratory of Grassland Agro-ecosystems, School of Life Sciences, Key
9 Laboratory for Semi-Arid Climate Change of the Ministry of Education, Lanzhou
10 University, No. 222, South Tianshui Road, Lanzhou 730000, China

11 ²Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences, University of
12 Colorado, Boulder, CO 80309, USA.

13 ³Departamento de Biología y Geología, Física y Química Inorgánica, Escuela
14 Superior de Ciencias Experimentales y Tecnología, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos,
15 Calle Tulipán Sin Número, Móstoles 28933, Spain.

16 ⁴Departamento de Ecología, Universidad de Alicante, 03690 San Vicente del Raspeig
17 (Alicante), Spain.

18

19 **Correspondence to:** J.-S. Y.; telephone, +86 13919145033; email address,
20 yejsh@lzu.edu.cn

21

22 **Keywords:** plant productivity, plant species richness, precipitation, arid climate, last
23 glacial maximum, nutrient stocks, nutrient transformation rates, palaeoclimate

24

25 **Paper type:** Primary Research Article

26 **Abstract**

27 Past vegetation and climatic conditions are known to influence current biodiversity
28 patterns. However, whether their legacy effects affect the provision of multiple
29 ecosystem functions, i.e. multifunctionality, remains largely unknown. Here we
30 analyzed soil nutrient stocks and their transformation rates in 236 drylands from six
31 continents to evaluate the associations between current levels of multifunctionality
32 and legacy effects of last glacial maximum (LGM) desert biome distribution and
33 climate. We found that past desert distribution and temperature legacy, defined as
34 increasing temperature from LGM, were negatively correlated with contemporary
35 multifunctionality even after accounting for predictors such as current climate, soil
36 texture, plant species richness and site topography. Ecosystems that have been deserts
37 since the LGM had up to 30% lower contemporary multifunctionality compared with
38 those that were non-deserts during the LGM. In addition, ecosystems that experienced
39 higher warming rates since the LGM had lower contemporary multifunctionality than
40 those suffering lower warming rates, with a ~9% reduction per extra °C. Past desert
41 distribution and temperature legacies had direct negative effects, while temperature
42 legacy also had indirect (via soil sand content) negative effects on multifunctionality.
43 Our results indicate that past biome and climatic conditions have left a strong
44 “functionality debt” in global drylands. They also suggest that ongoing warming and
45 expansion of desert areas may leave a strong fingerprint in the future functioning of
46 dryland ecosystems worldwide that needs to be considered when establishing
47 management actions aiming to combat land degradation and desertification.

48

49 **1. INTRODUCTION**

50 Ecosystem attributes and functions, such as biodiversity and nutrient cycling, are not
51 only driven by current environmental conditions, but also by those they have
52 experienced in the past. The climate existing thousands of years ago has left a
53 detectable fingerprint in the current distribution of plant and microbial communities
54 (Blonder et al., 2018; Delgado-Baquerizo, Bissett, et al., 2017; Delgado-Baquerizo et
55 al., 2018; Pärtel et al., 2017; Weigelt, Steinbauer, Cabral, & Kreft, 2016). Similarly,
56 changes in land use that occurred centuries ago have been found to affect current soil
57 carbon and nitrogen contents and cycling (Delgado-Baquerizo, Eldridge, et al., 2017;
58 Dupouey, Dambrine, Laffite, & Moares, 2002). Despite the growing evidence of the
59 impacts of past legacies on the contemporary structure and functioning of terrestrial
60 ecosystems, we lack empirical studies aiming to quantify the legacy effects of past
61 climate and biome distribution on the current provision of multiple ecosystem
62 functions (multifunctionality) related to nutrient stocks and their transformation rates.
63 Quantifying these legacy effects is important not only to better understand the factors
64 driving current variation in multifunctionality, but also to help foresee potential
65 limitations in the provision of ecosystem services in the future derived from current
66 rates of land degradation and climate change.

67 Legacy effects of past conditions on multifunctionality can be caused by
68 long-term gains and losses of energy and nutrients accumulated over millennia
69 (Delgado-Baquerizo, Eldridge, et al., 2017; Svenning, Eiserhardt, Normand, Ordonez,
70 & Sandel, 2015). Furthermore, past climate or vegetation have been found to affect
71 current patterns of soil texture and plant traits globally (Blonder et al., 2018; Prentice
72 et al., 1992). Soil texture and plant traits are known to influence ecosystem functions
73 (Blonder et al., 2018; Prentice et al., 1992). For example, loamy soils can carry over

74 moisture from the wet season into the dry season for plant production more effectively
75 than sandy soils (Prentice et al., 1992). Therefore, the legacy of past conditions on
76 multifunctionality can also be indirectly mediated by changes in variables including
77 soil texture (Prentice et al., 1992), plant functional traits (Blonder et al., 2018) and
78 microbial communities (Delgado-Baquerizo, Bissett, et al., 2017). Differentiating
79 between these direct and indirect effects is of crucial importance to better quantify
80 which part of legacy effects can be managed for (i.e., those mediated by biodiversity)
81 from those that cannot be buffered (i.e., the direct effect of past biome and climate
82 conditions).

83 Global drylands, including hyper-arid, arid, semi-arid and dry-subhumid
84 ecosystems, have been projected to experience higher warming rates with ongoing
85 climate change than humid areas (Huang, Yu, Dai, Wei, & Kang, 2017). Increases in
86 aridity due to ongoing global warming will increase the global extent of drylands,
87 which already cover ~45% of the terrestrial surface (Právělie, 2016), by 11-23% by
88 the end of this century (Huang, Yu, Guan, Wang, & Guo, 2016). Such aridification
89 will threaten the livelihoods of people living in these areas, particularly in the
90 developing world, and will exacerbate the risk of land degradation and desertification,
91 which are already negatively affecting 250 million people (Reynolds et al., 2007).

92 Given the inherently slow dynamics of soil nutrient buildup and plant
93 productivity in drylands compared to other ecosystems (Fischer & Turner, 1978;
94 Huang et al., 2017), we would expect strong negative legacy effects of past biome and
95 climate conditions on current multifunctionality levels, i.e. a “functionality debt”. The
96 desert biome is characterized by low vegetation cover, and thus high soil erosion rates
97 and low nutrient contents (Borrelli et al., 2017; Olson et al., 2001; Ray & Adams,
98 2001). Therefore, ecosystems under a desert biome thousands of years ago should

99 have lower multifunctionality than ecosystems under a more mesic biome in the same
100 period, regardless of their current climate and biome. However, the impact of these
101 legacy effects on dryland multifunctionality, as well as whether these effects are
102 biodiversity- and soil texture-dependent, remains to be evaluated. Moreover, the
103 relative importance of functionality debts vs. current climate and biome as drivers of
104 contemporary multifunctionality is largely unknown.

105 To address these gaps in our knowledge, we coupled data from a field survey of
106 236 drylands from six continents (Figure 1) to existing databases on the historical
107 distribution of past biomes and climates (Fick & Hijmans, 2017; Olson et al., 2001;
108 Ray & Adams, 2001) to evaluate the legacy effects of desert distribution and climate
109 during the last glacial maximum (LGM, about 22000 years ago) on current
110 multifunctionality levels. Weigelt et al. (2016) suggested that glacial conditions have
111 been more common than interglacial conditions during recent evolutionary time. The
112 distribution of biomes during the LGM is representative of the dominant
113 environmental conditions (including climate) during this period (Pärtel et al., 2017).
114 Therefore, the LGM biome distribution is likely to have a strong legacy effect on
115 current multifunctionality levels. We hypothesized that areas that have been under the
116 desert biome during LGM should have a reduced contemporary multifunctionality
117 compared to current deserts that were not so during the LGM (i.e. they exhibit a
118 functionality debt). Furthermore, Maestre et al. (2012) found that multifunctionality
119 was reduced with increasing temperature in global drylands. Therefore, we also
120 hypothesized that current drylands that have suffered higher increases in temperature
121 since the LGM will have lower multifunctionality when compared to those that have
122 undergone lower warming rates.

123

124 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

125 **2.1 Study sites**

126 We used data from a global field survey conducted in 236 dryland ecosystems from 19
127 countries (Figure 1, see also Table S1 in Supporting Information and Data S1). Our
128 field survey was limited by funding, accessibility to locations and geopolitical and
129 safety circumstances. Because of these, a truly global random sampling covering all
130 dryland locations worldwide was not possible. Nevertheless, our sampling aimed to
131 cover a large range of the environmental conditions and soil/vegetation types found in
132 dryland ecosystems worldwide. The 236 studied ecosystems cover a mean annual
133 temperature (MAT) ranging from -1.8 to 28.2 °C, and a mean annual precipitation
134 (MAP) ranging from 66 to 1219 mm. They also cover over 25 categories of soil types
135 from the FAO classification, including all main types present in drylands (Maestre et
136 al., 2012). The vegetation types surveyed include grasslands, shrublands and savannas,
137 and plant species richness varies from 1 to 52 species per 900 m².

138 **2.2 Field survey**

139 We carried out data collection between February 2006 and December 2013 using a
140 standardized sampling protocol. At each site, we surveyed vegetation using four
141 30-m-long transects located parallel and separated 10 m among them (see Maestre et
142 al., 2012 for details). At each transect, we established 20 quadrats of 1.5 m × 1.5 m
143 and used the total number of perennial species found within the 80 quadrats surveyed
144 as our estimation of species richness. We measured slope angle *in situ* with a
145 clinometer. We sampled soils during the dry season in most of the sites using a
146 stratified random procedure. At each plot, we randomly placed five 50 cm × 50 cm
147 quadrats under the canopy of the dominant perennial species and in open areas devoid
148 of perennial vegetation. We collected a composite sample consisting of five 145 cm³

149 soil cores (0 - 7.5 cm depth) from each quadrat, which were bulked and homogenized
150 in the field. When more than one dominant plant species was present, we also
151 collected samples under the canopies of five randomly selected individuals of the
152 co-dominant species. Thus, the number of soil samples varied between 10 and 15 per
153 site. Back in the laboratory, we sieved soil samples using a 2 mm mesh and air-dried
154 them for one month. To facilitate the comparison of results across sites, we shipped
155 the dried soil samples from all sites to Spain (Rey Juan Carlos University) for
156 laboratory analyses.

157 **2.3 Quantifying multifunctionality**

158 To quantify multifunctionality, we selected 12 plant and soil variables that act as
159 surrogates of carbon (C), nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) cycling and storage
160 (functions hereafter). Functions related to the C cycle included plant productivity, soil
161 organic C, pentoses and hexoses. Those from N and P cycles included soil nitrate,
162 dissolved organic N, proteins, potential N transformation rate, and enzymatic activity
163 of phosphatase, available inorganic P, total P and inorganic P. These variables are
164 considered to be critical measures of ecosystem functioning in drylands (see Whitford,
165 2002 for a review). We included as many functions as possible while at the same time
166 weighting equally for the three nutrient cycles. The functions selected include “true”
167 ecosystem functions (*sensu* Reiss, Bridle, Montoya, & Woodward, 2009), such as
168 potential N transformation rate, plant productivity and the activity of phosphatase,
169 and nutrient stocks such as soil organic C and total P, which are indicators of nutrient
170 cycling rates over the long term (Manning et al., 2018).

171 We assessed multifunctionality following the averaging approach of Maestre et al.
172 (2012). We averaged the Z scores of the 12 functions to obtain ecosystem
173 multifunctionality. This index is statistically robust (Maestre et al., 2012) and provides

174 a holistic and easily interpretable measure to assess changes in multifunctionality, as
175 the higher the values for the different ecosystem functions we measured, the higher
176 the multifunctionality (Figure S1). We acknowledge that using an *a priori*
177 standardized average may not allow to discriminate when all functions are performing
178 at similar levels from situations when one function could be strongly outperforming
179 the others (Byrnes et al., 2014). However, all individual functions in our dataset
180 positively correlated with multifunctionality, except for soil inorganic P ($r = -0.01$,
181 Figure S1). Moreover, we found only two negative correlations between the functions
182 that were of some magnitude ($r = -0.34$ and -0.35), suggesting that there are not
183 strong trade-offs between our surrogates of ecosystem functioning (Table S2). None
184 of the correlations across all 12 functions was higher than 0.6, suggesting that our
185 dataset did not contain high redundancy among the functions studied (Table S2).
186 Multifunctionality calculated from the 12 functions correlated well with that
187 calculated from a dataset of 16 functions ($r = 0.88$, Figure S2), thus it did not vary
188 much when including other functions available, such as soil total nitrogen, amino
189 acids, aromatic compounds or potential nitrogen depolymerisation.

190 We measured soil functions in the laboratory as described in Methods S1 in the
191 Supporting Information. We also measured soil pH with a pH-meter in a 1:2.5
192 (mass:volume, soil:water) suspension, and soil sand content according to Kettler et al.
193 (2001). For all soil variables and functions, we estimated site-level values as the mean
194 values measured in vegetated and open areas, weighted by their respective cover at
195 each site (Maestre et al., 2012). We used the normalized difference vegetation index
196 (NDVI) as a surrogate for plant productivity because it acts as a proxy of
197 photosynthetic activity and large-scale vegetation distribution (Pettorelli et al., 2005),
198 and it shows good performance vs. other vegetation indices when used in dryland

199 ecosystems such as those we studied (Gaitán et al., 2013). We retrieved NDVI data
200 from the 250 m resolution moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer (MODIS)
201 aboard NASA's Terra satellites (<http://daac.ornl.gov/index.shtml>). We used the annual
202 integral of NDVI (iNDVI, Ponce Campos et al., 2013) averaged for the period 2000 to
203 2013 as a proxy of plant productivity at our sites. These iNDVI values correlated well
204 with the average NDVI of the images before, during and after each soil and vegetation
205 survey (Pearson's $r = 0.76$, Figure S3). We used the longer term iNDVI as these
206 values are less influenced by short term variations in precipitation and temperature.

207 **2.4 Assessing biome and climatic legacies**

208 We obtained mean annual temperature and precipitation values for each site for both
209 current (1970-2000) and last glacial maximum (LGM; about 22000 years ago)
210 conditions from Worldclim (Fick & Hijmans, 2017). We used the 2.5-minute
211 resolution bioclimatic data for both periods, as 2.5-minute is the highest resolution
212 available for LGM data. We defined climate legacy from LGM as the difference
213 between current and LGM climate values for temperature and precipitation.
214 Temperature and precipitation legacies range from 2.7 °C to 10.7 °C (mean = 4.8 °C,
215 standard deviation = 1.6) and from -300 mm to +600 mm (mean = -14 mm, standard
216 deviation = 114) across sites, respectively.

217 We used the biome maps of Olson et al. (2001) and Ray & Adams (2001) to
218 define current and LGM distributions of desert biomes, respectively (Figure 1), which
219 included both tropical ($\leq 10\%$ vegetation cover) and temperate ($\leq 20\%$ vegetation
220 cover) deserts. The LGM biome map was mainly based on plant fossil data, proxy
221 data sources such as animal and sediment information and palaeoclimatic data (Ray &
222 Adams, 2001). The current biome map is based on the widely recognized global maps
223 of floristic or zoogeographic provinces, global maps of broad vegetation types,

224 consultations from regional experts, and current climatic data (Olson et al., 2001).

225 The current and LGM biome maps include 15 and 24 biomes, respectively.
226 Therefore, we regrouped LGM biomes to match the current classifications according
227 to Pärtel et al. (2017). The desert biome had a larger distribution during LGM than
228 nowadays (Figure 1). Spatially, the distribution of the desert biome largely overlaps
229 with that of arid and hyper-arid regions of the world (Figure 1). However, vegetation
230 distributions were impacted not only by climate (Thomas & Nigam, 2018) but also by
231 changes in sea level, large vertebrate migrations, fire disturbance regimes or
232 geological activity (Olson et al., 2001; Ray & Adams, 2001; Sarnthein, 1978).
233 Therefore, the desert biome is not synonymous with arid and hyper-arid climates
234 (Figure 1).

235 We defined desert legacy as a binary variable depending on whether it was a
236 desert (105 sites) or not (131 sites) during the LGM. Similarly, current desert
237 distribution is a binary variable depending on whether a given site is currently a desert
238 (63 sites) or not (173 sites). We included the two binomial variables in the statistical
239 analyses described below. The desert biomes were delineated based on thresholds of
240 both climate and key ecosystem properties such as vegetation cover (Olson et al.,
241 2001; Ray & Adams, 2001). When key ecosystem properties such as vegetation cover
242 are pushed over given thresholds, ecosystem regime shifts are likely to occur (here
243 from non-desert to desert, D’Odorico, Bhattachan, Davis, Ravi, & Runyan, 2013) and
244 its biodiversity and functions may be greatly altered (Hastings & Wysham, 2010;
245 Pardini, Bueno, Gardner, Prado, & Metzger, 2010). Therefore, the binary variable of
246 desert and non-desert should be a complement to the continuous climatic variables
247 being studied here.

248 **2.5 Statistical analyses**

249 We fitted a generalized least squares (gls) model using multifunctionality as our
250 response variable and desert and climate legacies, current desert and climate, soil pH
251 and sand content, plant species richness, and site elevation and slope as predictors.
252 This approach allows to incorporate in the model a spatial correlation structure to
253 account for the autocorrelation found within our 236 study sites. We evaluated gls
254 models with different spatial correlation structures using the Akaike information
255 criteria (AIC), and found that an exponential spatial correlation structure best
256 described the autocorrelation within the sites surveyed. The gls does not automatically
257 select predictive variables. Therefore, we first included all the potential predictor
258 variables, and then simplified the fitted model using a stepwise variable selection by
259 manually removing at each step the predictor with less explanatory power (Table 1).
260 Finally, we selected the best model with the lowest AIC (Burnham & Anderson, 2003;
261 Shipley, 2009). The semivariogram of the residuals of the final model used suggested
262 that our approach effectively removed spatial autocorrelation (Figure S4). These
263 analyses were carried out with the R package “nlme” version n 3.1-137 (Pinheiro,
264 Bates, DebRoy, Sarkar, & Team, 2012).

265 We then used variation partitioning (Legendre, 2008) based on linear regression
266 to identify the unique portion of variation in multifunctionality explained by four
267 groups of predictors: (1) LGM desert legacy, (2) temperature and precipitation
268 legacies, (3) current temperature, precipitation and desert distribution, and (4) other
269 drivers (location, soil, plant, and site elevation and slope). The variation partitioning
270 approach followed uses partial regression to partition the variance in
271 multifunctionality with respect to the four groups of predictors. Some proportions
272 were attributed to a particular group of predictors (unique variation) and some were
273 shared among all predictors (shared variation). We used adjusted coefficients of

274 determination (R^2) in the variation partitioning to account for the different number of
275 predictors included in each of the four categories. In some cases, the adjusted R^2 can
276 be negative, which means that the predictors explained less variation than expected by
277 chance (Legendre, 2008); we set them to zero. We used permutation tests for
278 redundancy analysis ordination, as described in Oksanen et al. (2018), to test the
279 significance of unique variation explained by each group; the significance of the
280 shared variation was not testable. We conducted variation partitioning analyses using
281 the R package “Vegan” version 2.4-5 (Oksanen et al., 2018).

282 We used confirmatory path analysis (CPA) to further investigate the direct and
283 indirect (via plant species richness and soil properties) effects of current and LGM
284 climates and desert distributions on the multifunctionality of the 236 drylands studied.
285 CPA allows the analysis of multiple variables that can present complex dependencies
286 among them, which enabled us to partition the direct and indirect effects of different
287 predictors (Shipley, 2009). We developed an *a priori* CPA model (Figure S5) that
288 included all the relationships based on previous knowledge of the potential
289 relationships between our variables (Delgado-Baquerizo, Bissett, et al., 2017;
290 Soliveres et al., 2014). We included in the CPA generalized least squares (gls) fitting
291 of multifunctionality, plant/soil variables and their predictor variables (Figure S5). We
292 then simplified the CPA by removing non-significant paths and selected the best
293 model as that having the lowest AIC. The final CPA included a gls fitting using
294 multifunctionality as response variable and the desert and temperature legacies,
295 current temperature, soil sand content, and elevation as predictors, and a second gls
296 fitting using soil sand content as response variable and the temperature legacy, current
297 temperature and precipitation, and as predictors. Since we included the spatial
298 correlation structure within all gls included in the model, CPA also effectively

299 removed the potential autocorrelation among our sites (Figure S6). We conducted
300 CPA using the R package “piecewiseSEM” version 2.0.2 (Lefcheck, 2016).

301 We checked the normality of all variables before and after log- and square-root
302 transformations using the Shapiro-Wilk test as implemented in R, version 3.5.1 (Team,
303 2018). We then selected the transformation that allowed a best fit to a normal
304 distribution for each variable. To address the quadratic relationships observed between
305 multifunctionality and both soil pH and site elevation (Figure S7), we included x and
306 x^2 terms in all statistical analyses, where x is either pH or elevation. We selected the
307 quadratic model over the linear one if the Δ of differences in AIC between these two
308 models, i.e. AIC linear – AIC quadratic, was larger than two (Burnham & Anderson,
309 2003).

310 As recommended (Byrnes et al., 2014; Manning et al., 2018), and to help
311 interpreting our results, we also repeated CPA analyses for all 12 measured functions
312 separately to test whether the effects of climate and biome legacies were consistent on
313 the overall multifunctionality and individual functions (Table 2). Moreover, we
314 conducted CPA for rate- and stock-based multifunctionality, respectively, to test
315 whether the legacy effects were consistent between nutrient stocks and their
316 transformation rates.

317 Plant functional diversity is a major driver of dryland multifunctionality (Gross et
318 al., 2017) that is also likely to be affected by past climate and biome distribution
319 (Blonder et al., 2018). Hence, we also retrieved trait data for two key traits, plant
320 height and specific leaf area, from the TRY database (Kattge et al., 2011) as described
321 in Gross et al. (2017). A total of 123 of the 236 sites surveyed had trait information
322 available (Gross et al., 2017). We also conducted a CPA using these 123 sites to
323 control for potential indirect effects of past conditions on current multifunctionality

324 driven by functional traits. Including trait predictors did not essentially affect our
325 results (Figure S8). However, among the 123 sites with trait information only fifteen
326 are desert biome currently. Such small sample sizes decreased our confidence when
327 testing the hypothesis of functionality debt caused by desert legacies. Therefore, we
328 only present the results using all 236 sites in the main text. We also controlled for
329 regional differences in other potential confounding factors such as human influence
330 (i.e., population pressure and land use; Last of the Wild Data, 2005), by using the
331 residuals after fitting multifunctionality vs. human influence index (Figure S9).

332

333 **3. RESULTS**

334 We found a significant negative association between desert legacy and current
335 ecosystem multifunctionality. The mean multifunctionality was 30% ($\pm 6\%$) lower in
336 drylands that were deserts during LGM than those were not (Table 1). Temperature
337 legacy was also negatively and significantly associated with multifunctionality; this
338 variable was reduced by $\sim 9\%$ per degree warming (Table 1). In other words,
339 regardless of their past biome distribution, locations with the largest increases in
340 temperature over the last 22K years had the lowest multifunctionality. Similarly,
341 current temperature was also negatively and significantly associated with
342 multifunctionality, albeit the rate of decrease ($\sim 2\%$ lower per degree warming) was
343 much lower than that observed with temperature legacy (Table 1). Soil sand content
344 was negatively related to multifunctionality (Table 1).

345 Both desert and climate legacies explained unique and significant proportions of
346 variation in multifunctionality (13% in total, Figure 2). Interestingly, current climates
347 and desert distribution explained a small ($< 3\%$), albeit statistically significant ($P <$
348 0.01), unique proportion of variation. Additional environmental predictors including

349 soil, geographical, and plant variables explained the highest unique proportion of
350 variation in multifunctionality (~ 33%). The shared variation among all predictors was
351 around 2% (Figure 2).

352 Our confirmatory path analysis explained ~43% of the variation in
353 multifunctionality (Figure 3a). It confirmed the strong negative associations between
354 contemporary multifunctionality and past desert distribution and temperatures, even
355 after considering major drivers of dryland multifunctionality such as current climate,
356 soil properties, site topography, plant species richness, functional diversity and human
357 influence (Figures 3 and S8-9). These negative associations were driven by the effects
358 found both on nutrient stocks, such as soil organic carbon, and their transformation
359 rates, such as plant productivity (Table 2), indicating that both were equally sensitive
360 to legacy effects. The negative effects of desert and temperature legacies were also
361 consistent for 60% of the individual functions (vs. only 13% positive effects, Table 2),
362 and when including more functions in our analyses (16 instead of 12 functions, Figure
363 S10). We found that LGM desert and temperature legacies had strong negative direct
364 effects on multifunctionality, which were about 250% stronger than those found for
365 current climate and desert distribution (Figure 3a). Temperature legacies also had
366 indirect (via positive effect on soil sand content) negative effects on multifunctionality
367 (Figure 3a). Desert and climate legacies had a ~ 10% larger standardized total effect
368 (i.e. sum of indirect and direct effects) on multifunctionality than current desert and
369 climate (Figure 3b).

370 Current temperature had both direct and indirect (via soil sand content) negative
371 effects on multifunctionality (Figure 3a). It also had negative effects on about 70% of
372 the individual functions (Table 2). Current precipitation positively and indirectly
373 influenced multifunctionality through the effects on soil sand content, albeit its effects

374 were only about 25% of the respective effect size of desert and temperature legacies
375 (Figure 3b). Soil sand content negatively impacted multifunctionality (Figure 3a); it
376 also had negative effects on seven individual functions (vs. only one positive effect,
377 Table 2). Biodiversity had no significant effects on overall multifunctionality,
378 although it significantly and positively impacted soil organic C, soil hexoses and soil
379 enzymatic activity of phosphatase (Table 2). However, when multifunctionality was
380 calculated based on a different set of functions (16 stocks and rates, Figure S10), we
381 found a positive effect of species richness on multifunctionality.

382

383 **4. DISCUSSION**

384 Our work provides empirical evidence of a long-term functionality debt in global
385 drylands promoted by legacy effects of past temperature and desert biome distribution.
386 These results add to the increasing evidence that past conditions largely influence
387 current ecosystem structure and functioning (Delgado-Baquerizo, Eldridge, et al.,
388 2017; Monger et al., 2015; Ogle et al., 2015; Pärtel et al., 2017), and provide novel
389 insights about the potential impacts of the climatic changes occurring today for future
390 ecosystem functioning. Importantly, here we found that the negative association
391 between legacy effects and multifunctionality was not only related to stocks but also
392 to nutrient transformation rates, which are fundamental components of ecosystem
393 functioning. Moreover, past legacies had always larger effects on multifunctionality
394 than those of current biomes and climate, which cautions about the potential
395 underestimation of the functional consequences of current warming rates, as the total
396 effects may take some time to manifest. Climatic legacy effects were mainly driven by
397 increases in temperature rather than by changes in rainfall, suggesting that ongoing
398 global warming may have a more detrimental effect on the future of dryland

399 multifunctionality than forecasted changes in rainfall patterns.

400 There are several mechanisms explaining the legacy effects of past biome and
401 climate on both stock- and rate-based functions. First, past climate is known to have
402 an effect on soil texture (our results, Prentice et al., 1992) and also on current
403 microbial diversity and plant functional traits patterns (Blonder et al., 2018;
404 Delgado-Baquerizo, Bissett, et al., 2017), which are important factors influencing
405 nutrient flux rates and primary productivity in drylands (Delgado-Baquerizo et al.,
406 2016; Gross et al., 2017). Second, past climate and biome distribution may drive
407 biotic inputs on soils for millennia, something likely to have a substantial influence on
408 current nutrient stocks. This has been previously observed for soil C
409 (Delgado-Baquerizo, Eldridge, et al., 2017) and we found similar results for both N
410 and P stocks. Third, nutrient stocks and their transformation rates are interdependent.
411 The rates of nutrient fluxes are affected not only by current environmental factors
412 such as climate and vegetation type, but also the size of nutrient stocks (Shen,
413 Jenerette, Hui, & Scott, 2016). For example, many ecosystems in drylands are N
414 limited, and thus their rate of primary productivity are influenced by soil N stocks
415 (Harpole, Potts, & Suding, 2007). Nitrogen transformation rate is positively affected
416 by the size of microbial biomass (Chen et al., 2017), which is generally C limited
417 (Conant et al., 2011); therefore, N transformation rate is likely to be positively
418 affected by soil C and N stocks, as already observed in our database
419 (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2013). Therefore, changes in nutrient stocks caused by past
420 climate and biome conditions are likely to affect current nutrient transformation rates
421 (see Table 2). In addition to the potential mechanisms behind the legacy effects of past
422 climate, desert biomes are characterized by low vegetation cover and productivity,
423 high soil erosion rates, extremely slow rates of soil formation, reduced nutrient

424 turnover and slow recovery after disturbances (Borrelli et al., 2017; Chandler, Day,
425 Madsen, & Belnap, 2019; Webb, 2002). These characteristics might contribute to the
426 negative legacy effects from past desert distribution observed in our study. It has been
427 estimated that the recovery of ecosystem functioning after anthropogenic disturbances
428 may take from centuries to millenia in drylands (Belnap & Warren, 2002; Lovich &
429 Bainbridge, 1999). Although these examples show legacy effects from relatively
430 shorter timescales compared to that found in our study, they illustrate the inherent
431 slow dynamics in ecosystem functioning typically observed in drylands, and may
432 suggest similar slow recovery after natural disturbances such as climate variation and
433 biome migration.

434 Our findings indicate that a reversal from desert to more mesic biomes may still
435 be impacted by a functionality debt from its past condition. Recovering a disturbed
436 ecosystem might take from centuries to thousands of years, and an interim recovery
437 debt (the reduction of ecosystem functions occurring during ecosystem recovery after
438 disturbance) will accumulate even if complete recovery is reached (Moreno-Mateos et
439 al., 2017). A recent meta-analysis has shown that ecosystems recovering from
440 anthropogenic disturbances such as agricultural transformation and mining had over
441 35% lower C and N stocks compared with “undisturbed” reference areas
442 (Moreno-Mateos et al., 2017). Our results show a “functionality debt” (~30% decline
443 in multifunctionality) of previous environmental conditions associated to desertified
444 drylands, i.e. high aridity and low vegetation cover. Although they are based on past
445 climate and biome distribution, and thus may not necessarily extrapolate into the
446 future, they suggest that the rate of land restoration should consider this functionality
447 debt and exceed that of land degradation by a similar amount to achieve zero net land
448 degradation aimed by international initiatives such as the UNCCD (UNCCD, 2012).

449 Warming reduces soil moisture, and thus inhibits microbial activity, nutrient
450 cycling, plant growth and vegetation cover in drylands (Foley, Costa, Delire,
451 Ramankutty, & Snyder, 2003; Huang et al., 2017; Yin, Roderick, Leech, Sun, &
452 Huang, 2014). Reduction in vegetation cover also increases soil erosion (Casermeiro
453 et al., 2004; Wei et al., 2007), affecting soil texture and thus promoting soil-mediated
454 temperature legacy effects. Therefore, sites experiencing higher warming rates from
455 LGM to current climate have lower multifunctionality than those suffering lower
456 warming rates (Figure 3). Huang et al. (2017; 2016) predicted deleterious effects of
457 ongoing global warming on the world's drylands, including long-lasting droughts and
458 reduced crop yields and carbon sequestration in the future. In a similar direction, our
459 results provide empirical evidence that a warming from past to today is negatively
460 associated with multiple functions in dryland ecosystems worldwide.

461 Together, our study provides novel evidence that past desert and temperature
462 legacies have detectable imprints on the current multifunctionality of global drylands.
463 They highlight the importance of looking not only at current but past conditions to
464 fully understand current multifunctionality patterns in these ecosystems. Our results
465 also suggest that ongoing climate change, which will increase the expansion of desert
466 areas, might substantially compromise the multifunctionality of global drylands in the
467 future, and that the rate of land restoration should exceed that of land degradation by
468 around one third if we aim to maintain the ecosystem functions that underpin the
469 provision of key services for the 38% of human population in a warmer, and more arid,
470 world.

471

472 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

473 J.-S.Y. is supported by China Scholarship Council and the National Natural Science

474 Foundation of China (31570467). MDB acknowledges support from the Marie
475 Skłodowska-Curie Actions of the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme
476 H2020-MSCA-IF-2016 under REA grant agreement n° 702057. SS is supported by
477 the Spanish Government under a Ramón y Cajal contract (RYC-2016-20604). This
478 research is supported by the European Research Council (ERC Grant Agreements
479 242658 [BIOCOM] and 647038 [BIODESERT]).

480

481 **REFERENCES**

482 Belnap, J., & Warren, S. D. (2002). Patton's Tracks in the Mojave Desert, USA: An
483 Ecological Legacy. *Arid Land Research and Management*, 16(3), 245-258.
484 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/153249802760284793>

485 Blonder, B., Enquist, B. J., Graae, B. J., Kattge, J., Maitner, B. S., Morueta-Holme,
486 N., . . . Violle, C. (2018). Late Quaternary climate legacies in contemporary
487 plant functional composition. *Global Change Biology*, 24(10), 4827-4840.
488 doi:[doi:10.1111/gcb.14375](https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14375)

489 Borrelli, P., Robinson, D. A., Fleischer, L. R., Lugato, E., Ballabio, C., Alewell,
490 C., . . . Panagos, P. (2017). An assessment of the global impact of 21st century
491 land use change on soil erosion. *Nature Communications*, 8(1), 2013.
492 doi:[10.1038/s41467-017-02142-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02142-7)

493 Burnham, K. P., & Anderson, D. R. (2003). *Model selection and multimodel inference:
494 a practical information-theoretic approach*: Springer Science & Business
495 Media.

496 Byrnes, J. E. K., Gamfeldt, L., Isbell, F., Lefcheck, J. S., Griffin, J. N., Hector, A., . . .
497 Emmett, D. J. (2014). Investigating the relationship between biodiversity and
498 ecosystem multifunctionality: challenges and solutions. *Methods in Ecology*

499 *and Evolution*, 5(2), 111-124. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12143>

500 Casermeiro, M. A., Molina, J. A., de la Cruz Caravaca, M. T., Hernando Costa, J.,
501 Hernando Massanet, M. I., & Moreno, P. S. (2004). Influence of scrubs on
502 runoff and sediment loss in soils of Mediterranean climate. *CATENA*, 57(1),
503 91-107. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0341-8162\(03\)00160-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0341-8162(03)00160-7)

504 Chandler, D. G., Day, N., Madsen, M. D., & Belnap, J. (2019). Amendments fail to
505 hasten biocrust recovery or soil stability at a disturbed dryland sandy site.
506 *Restoration Ecology*, 0(0). doi:[doi:10.1111/rec.12870](https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.12870)

507 Chen, J., Xiao, G., Kuzyakov, Y., Jenerette, G. D., Ma, Y., Liu, W., . . . Shen, W.
508 (2017). Soil nitrogen transformation responses to seasonal precipitation
509 changes are regulated by changes in functional microbial abundance in a
510 subtropical forest. *Biogeosciences*, 14(9), 2513-2525.
511 doi:<https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-14-2513-2017>

512 Conant, R. T., Ryan, M. G., Ågren, G. I., Birge, H. E., Davidson, E. A., Eliasson, P.
513 E., . . . Hopkins, F. M. (2011). Temperature and soil organic matter
514 decomposition rates—synthesis of current knowledge and a way forward.
515 *Global Change Biology*, 17(11), 3392-3404.

516 D’Odorico, P., Bhattachan, A., Davis, K. F., Ravi, S., & Runyan, C. W. (2013).
517 Global desertification: Drivers and feedbacks. *Advances in Water Resources*,
518 51, 326-344. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2012.01.013>

519 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Bissett, A., Eldridge, D. J., Maestre, F. T., He, J.-Z., Wang,
520 J.-T., . . . Fierer, N. (2017). Palaeoclimate explains a unique proportion of the
521 global variation in soil bacterial communities. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*,
522 1(9), 1339-1347. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0259-7>

523 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Eldridge, D. J., Maestre, F. T., Karunaratne, S. B., Trivedi, P.,

524 Reich, P. B., & Singh, B. K. (2017). Climate legacies drive global soil carbon
525 stocks in terrestrial ecosystems. *Science Advances*, 3(4).
526 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1602008>

527 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Eldridge, D. J., Travers, S. K., Val, J., Oliver, I., & Bissett, A.
528 (2018). Effects of climate legacies on above- and belowground community
529 assembly. *Global Change Biology*, *in press*. doi:[doi:10.1111/gcb.14306](https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14306)

530 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Maestre, F. T., Gallardo, A., Bowker, M. A., Wallenstein, M.
531 D., Quero, J. L., . . . Zaady, E. (2013). Decoupling of soil nutrient cycles as a
532 function of aridity in global drylands. *Nature*, 502, 672.
533 doi:[10.1038/nature12670](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature12670)

534 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Maestre, F. T., Reich, P. B., Jeffries, T. C., Gaitan, J. J.,
535 Encinar, D., . . . Singh, B. K. (2016). Microbial diversity drives
536 multifunctionality in terrestrial ecosystems. *Nature Communications*, 7, 10541.
537 doi:[10.1038/ncomms10541](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10541)

538 <https://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms10541#supplementary-information>

539 Dupouey, J. L., Dambrine, E., Laffite, J. D., & Moares, C. (2002). Irreversible Impact
540 of past Land Use on Forest Soils and Biodiversity. *Ecology*, 83(11),
541 2978-2984. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/3071833>

542 Fick, S. E., & Hijmans, R. J. (2017). WorldClim 2: new 1-km spatial resolution
543 climate surfaces for global land areas. *International Journal of Climatology*,
544 37(12), 4302-4315. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5086>

545 Fischer, R. A., & Turner, N. C. (1978). Plant Productivity in the Arid and Semiarid
546 Zones. *Annual Review of Plant Physiology*, 29(1), 277-317.
547 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.pp.29.060178.001425>

548 Foley, J. A., Costa, M. H., Delire, C., Ramankutty, N., & Snyder, P. (2003). Green

549 Surprise? How Terrestrial Ecosystems Could Affect Earth's Climate. *Frontiers*
550 *in Ecology and the Environment*, *1*(1), 38-44.
551 doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/3867963>

552 Gaitán, J. J., Bran, D., Oliva, G., Ciari, G., Nakamatsu, V., Salomone, J., . . . Maestre,
553 F. T. (2013). Evaluating the performance of multiple remote sensing indices to
554 predict the spatial variability of ecosystem structure and functioning in
555 Patagonian steppes. *Ecological Indicators*, *34*, 181-191.
556 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2013.05.007>

557 Grace, J. B. (2006). *Structural equation modeling and natural systems*. Cambridge,
558 UK: Cambridge University Press.

559 Gross, N., Bagousse-Pinguet, Y. L., Liancourt, P., Berdugo, M., Gotelli, N. J., &
560 Maestre, F. T. (2017). Functional trait diversity maximizes ecosystem
561 multifunctionality. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, *1*, 0132.
562 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0132>

563 Harpole, W. S., Potts, D. L., & Suding, K. N. (2007). Ecosystem responses to water
564 and nitrogen amendment in a California grassland. *Global Change Biology*,
565 *13*(11), 2341-2348.

566 Hastings, A., & Wysham, D. B. (2010). Regime shifts in ecological systems can occur
567 with no warning. *Ecology Letters*, *13*(4), 464-472.
568 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2010.01439.x>

569 Huang, J., Yu, H., Dai, A., Wei, Y., & Kang, L. (2017). Drylands face potential threat
570 under 2 °C global warming target. *Nature Climate Change*, *7*, 417.
571 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3275>

572 Huang, J., Yu, H., Guan, X., Wang, G., & Guo, R. (2016). Accelerated dryland
573 expansion under climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, *6*, 166–171.

574 doi:10.1038/nclimate2837
575 <https://www.nature.com/articles/nclimate2837#supplementary-information>
576 Kattge, J., DÍAZ, S., LAVOREL, S., PRENTICE, I. C., LEADLEY, P., BÖNISCH,
577 G., . . . WIRTH, C. (2011). TRY – a global database of plant traits. *Global*
578 *Change Biology*, 17(9), 2905-2935.
579 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02451.x>
580 Kettler, T. A., Doran, J. W., & Gilbert, T. L. (2001). Simplified method for soil
581 particle-size determination to accompany soil-quality analyses. *Soil Science*
582 *Society of America Journal*, 65(3), 849-852.
583 doi:<https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2001.653849x>
584 Last of the Wild Data. (2005). *Wildlife Conservation Society - WCS, Center for*
585 *International Earth Science Information Network - CIESIN - Columbia*
586 *University, Last of the Wild Project, Version 2, 2005 (LWP-2): Global Human*
587 *Influence Index (HII) Dataset (Geographic)*. Palisades, NY: NASA
588 Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC).
589 Lefcheck, J. S. (2016). piecewiseSEM: Piecewise structural equation modelling in r
590 for ecology, evolution, and systematics. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*,
591 7(5), 573-579.
592 Legendre, P. (2008). Studying beta diversity: ecological variation partitioning by
593 multiple regression and canonical analysis. *Journal of Plant Ecology*, 1(1), 3-8.
594 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/jpe/rtm001>
595 Lovich, J. E., & Bainbridge, D. (1999). Anthropogenic Degradation of the Southern
596 California Desert Ecosystem and Prospects for Natural Recovery and
597 Restoration. *Environmental Management*, 24(3), 309-326.
598 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s002679900235>

599 Maestre, F. T., Quero, J. L., Gotelli, N. J., Escudero, A., Ochoa, V.,
600 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., . . . Zaady, E. (2012). Plant Species Richness and
601 Ecosystem Multifunctionality in Global Drylands. *Science*, *335*(6065),
602 214-218. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1215442>

603 Manning, P., van der Plas, F., Soliveres, S., Allan, E., Maestre, F. T., Mace, G., . . .
604 Fischer, M. (2018). Redefining ecosystem multifunctionality. *Nature Ecology
605 & Evolution*, *2*(3), 427-436. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0461-7>

606 Monger, C., Sala, O. E., Duniway, M. C., Goldfus, H., Meir, I. A., Poch, R. M., . . .
607 Vivoni, E. R. (2015). Legacy effects in linked ecological–soil–geomorphic
608 systems of drylands. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, *13*(1), 13-19.
609 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1890/140269>

610 Moreno-Mateos, D., Barbier, E. B., Jones, P. C., Jones, H. P., Aronson, J.,
611 López-López, J. A., . . . Rey Benayas, J. M. (2017). Anthropogenic ecosystem
612 disturbance and the recovery debt. *Nature Communications*, *8*, 14163.
613 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14163>

614 Ogle, K., Barber, J. J., Barron Gafford, G. A., Bentley, L. P., Young, J. M., Huxman,
615 T. E., . . . Tissue, D. T. (2015). Quantifying ecological memory in plant and
616 ecosystem processes. *Ecology Letters*, *18*(3), 221-235.
617 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12399>

618 Oksanen, J., Blanchet, F. G., Friendly, M., Kindt, R., Legendre, P., McGlinn, D., . . .
619 Wagner, H. (2018). *Community Ecology Package. R package v. 2.4-6.*

620 Olson, D. M., Dinerstein, E., Wikramanayake, E. D., Burgess, N. D., Powell, G. V. N.,
621 Underwood, E. C., . . . Kassem, K. R. (2001). Terrestrial Ecoregions of the
622 World: A New Map of Life on Earth. *BioScience*, *51*(11), 933-938.
623 doi:[https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2001\)051\[0933:teotwa\]2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2001)051[0933:teotwa]2.0.co;2)

624 Pärtel, M., Öpik, M., Moora, M., Tedersoo, L., Szava-Kovats, R., Rosendahl, S., . . .
625 Zobel, M. (2017). Historical biome distribution and recent human disturbance
626 shape the diversity of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. *New Phytologist*, *216*(1),
627 227-238. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.14695>

628 Pardini, R., Bueno, A. d. A., Gardner, T. A., Prado, P. I., & Metzger, J. P. (2010).
629 Beyond the Fragmentation Threshold Hypothesis: Regime Shifts in
630 Biodiversity Across Fragmented Landscapes. *PLOS ONE*, *5*(10), e13666.
631 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0013666>

632 Pettorelli, N., Vik, J. O., Mysterud, A., Gaillard, J.-M., Tucker, C. J., & Stenseth, N.
633 C. (2005). Using the satellite-derived NDVI to assess ecological responses to
634 environmental change. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, *20*(9), 503-510.
635 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2005.05.011>

636 Pinheiro, J., Bates, D., DebRoy, S., Sarkar, D., & Team, R. C. (2012). nlme: Linear
637 and nonlinear mixed effects models. *R package version*, *3*(0).

638 Ponce Campos, G. E., Moran, M. S., Huete, A., Zhang, Y., Bresloff, C., Huxman, T.
639 E., . . . Starks, P. J. (2013). Ecosystem resilience despite large-scale altered
640 hydroclimatic conditions. *Nature*, *494*(7437), 349-352.
641 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11836>

642 Právělie, R. (2016). Drylands extent and environmental issues. A global approach.
643 *Earth-Science Reviews*, *161*, 259-278.
644 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2016.08.003>

645 Prentice, I. C., Cramer, W., Harrison, S. P., Leemans, R., Monserud, R. A., &
646 Solomon, A. M. (1992). Special Paper: A Global Biome Model Based on Plant
647 Physiology and Dominance, Soil Properties and Climate. *Journal of*
648 *Biogeography*, *19*(2), 117-134. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/2845499>

649 Ray, N., & Adams, J. (2001). A GIS-based vegetation map of the world at the Last
650 Glacial Maximum (25,000-15,000 BP). *Internet Archaeology*, *11*.
651 doi:<https://doi.org/10.11141/ia.11.2>

652 Reiss, J., Bridle, J. R., Montoya, J. M., & Woodward, G. (2009). Emerging horizons
653 in biodiversity and ecosystem functioning research. *Trends in Ecology &*
654 *Evolution*, *24*(9), 505-514. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.03.018>

655 Reynolds, J. F., Smith, D. M. S., Lambin, E. F., Turner, B. L., Mortimore, M.,
656 Batterbury, S. P. J., . . . Walker, B. (2007). Global Desertification: Building a
657 Science for Dryland Development. *Science*, *316*(5826), 847-851.
658 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1131634>

659 Sarnthein, M. (1978). Sand deserts during glacial maximum and climatic optimum.
660 *Nature*, *272*, 43. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/272043a0>

661 Shen, W., Jenerette, D. G., Hui, D., & Scott, L. R. (2016). Precipitation legacy effects
662 on dryland ecosystem carbon fluxes: Direction, magnitude and
663 biogeochemical carryovers. *12*, 9613-9650.
664 doi:<https://doi.org/10.5194/bgd-12-9613-2015>

665 Shipley, B. (2009). Confirmatory path analysis in a generalized multilevel context.
666 *Ecology*, *90*(2), 363-368. doi:[doi:10.1890/08-1034.1](https://doi.org/10.1890/08-1034.1)

667 Soliveres, S., Maestre, F. T., Eldridge, D. J., Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Quero, J. L.,
668 Bowker, M. A., & Gallardo, A. (2014). Plant diversity and ecosystem
669 multifunctionality peak at intermediate levels of woody cover in global
670 drylands. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, *23*(12), 1408-1416.
671 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12215>

672 Svenning, J.-C., Eiserhardt, W. L., Normand, S., Ordonez, A., & Sandel, B. (2015).
673 The Influence of Paleoclimate on Present-Day Patterns in Biodiversity and

674 Ecosystems. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 46(1),
675 551-572. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-112414-054314>

676 Team, R. C. (2018). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing, R
677 Foundation for Statistical Computing, Austria, 2015. In: ISBN 3-900051-07-0:
678 URL <http://www.R-project.org>.

679 Thomas, N., & Nigam, S. (2018). Twentieth-Century Climate Change over Africa:
680 Seasonal Hydroclimate Trends and Sahara Desert Expansion. *Journal of*
681 *Climate*, 31(9), 3349-3370. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1175/jcli-d-17-0187.1>

682 Trabucco, A., & Zomer, R. J. (2009). *Global Aridity Index (Global-Aridity) and*
683 *Global Potential Evapo-Transpiration (Global-PET) Geospatial Database.*
684 *CGIAR Consortium for Spatial Information. Published online, available from*
685 *the CGIAR-CSI GeoPortal at: <http://www.csi.cgiar.org>.* Retrieved from:
686 <http://www.csi.cgiar.org>

687 UNCCD. (2012). Zero Net Land Degradation. A Sustainable Development Goal for
688 Rio+ 20. *Policy Brief, May*.

689 Webb, R. H. (2002). Recovery of Severely Compacted Soils in the Mojave Desert,
690 California, USA. *Arid Land Research and Management*, 16(3), 291-305.
691 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/153249802760284829>

692 Wei, W., Chen, L., Fu, B., Huang, Z., Wu, D., & Gui, L. (2007). The effect of land
693 uses and rainfall regimes on runoff and soil erosion in the semi-arid loess hilly
694 area, China. *Journal of Hydrology*, 335(3), 247-258.
695 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2006.11.016>

696 Weigelt, P., Steinbauer, M. J., Cabral, J. S., & Kreft, H. (2016). Late Quaternary
697 climate change shapes island biodiversity. *Nature*, 532, 99.
698 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/nature17443>

699 Whitford, W. G. (2002). *Ecology of desert systems*: Elsevier.
700 Yin, D., Roderick, M. L., Leech, G., Sun, F., & Huang, Y. (2014). The contribution of
701 reduction in evaporative cooling to higher surface air temperatures during
702 drought. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *41*(22), 7891-7897.
703 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/2014GL062039>

704

705 **Supporting Information**

706 Additional Supporting Information, including Figures S1-10, Method S1 and Tables
707 S1 and S2, may be found online in the supporting information tab for this article.

708

709 **Data availability**

710 Data in the support of these findings (Data S1) and the R code for the statistical
711 models conducted are available in figshare (DOI 10.6084/m9.figshare.7570925,
712 <https://figshare.com/s/4985715ce88482a9c460>).

713

714 **Table 1** Coefficients of the generalized least squares model fitted to assess the effect
715 of different predictor variables on ecosystem multifunctionality. This model included
716 a spatial correlation structure to account for the autocorrelation present within the 236
717 sites surveyed. We also removed the predictors with low power and the final model
718 had the lowest Akaike information criteria (see Methods section for details). The
719 predictor variables with significant explanatory power ($P < 0.05$) included desert
720 legacy, mean annual temperature (MAT) legacy, current MAT, soil sand content, and
721 site elevation (Elevation², square of elevation).

Predictor variables	Coefficients (mean \pm standard error)	<i>P</i>-value
Intercept	1.591 \pm 0.170	<0.001
Desert legacy	-0.295 \pm 0.061	<0.001
MAT legacy	-0.085 \pm 0.017	<0.001
Current MAT	-0.021 \pm 0.006	<0.001
Soil sand content	-0.011 \pm 0.001	<0.001
Elevation ²	0.001 \pm 0.000	0.009

722
723

724 **Table 2** The total standardized effects (direct + indirect) of desert legacy, climate legacy, and current desert and climate on 12 individual
725 ecosystem functions, based on the significant path coefficients ($P < 0.05$) of confirmatory path analyses. SOC, soil organic carbon; PEN, soil
726 pentoses; iNDVI, annual integral of normalized difference vegetation index; HEX, soil hexoses; NIT, soil nitrate; DON, soil dissolved organic
727 nitrogen; PRO, soil proteins; NTR, soil potential nitrogen transformation rate; AVP, soil available inorganic phosphorus; FOS, soil enzymatic
728 activity of phosphatase; TP, soil total phosphorus; IOP, soil inorganic phosphorus; MAT, mean annual temperature; MAP, annual precipitation;
729 Species, plant species richness; Sand, soil sand content; and site elevation (Elevation², square of elevation).

	SOC	iNDVI	PEN	HEX	NIT	DON	PRO	NTR	AVP	FOS	TP	IOP
Desert legacy	-0.21	-0.19	0	-0.33	0	0	0	0	0	-0.12	-0.19	0
MAT legacy	-0.19	-0.13	-0.37	-0.27	-0.12	0.43	-0.35	-0.1	0.12	-0.28	-0.39	0.08
MAP legacy	-0.01	-0.14	-0.33	0	0.35	0	0	0	0.2	-0.13	0.22	0.14
Current desert	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.19	-0.14	0	0
Current MAT	-0.62	0	-0.61	-0.18	-0.27	0.32	0	-0.36	-0.33	-0.64	-0.75	0.07
Current MAP	0.27	0.58	0	0.53	-0.03	0.07	-0.37	0.11	-0.34	0.46	0.14	-0.32
Species	0.16	0	0	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0.09	0	0

Sand	-0.47	0	0	-0.16	-0.32	-0.16	0	-0.24	0	-0.34	-0.3	0.21
pH	0.31	0	0	0.2	0	0	0.24	0	0	0.28	0	0
pH ²	-0.34	0	0	-0.22	0	0	0	0	0	-0.31	0	0
Elevation	-0.09	0.48	-0.52	-0.05	-0.14	0.44	0.68	0	0	0	0	0
Elevation ²	0.23	-0.74	0	-0.08	-0.16	-0.07	-0.67	-0.32	0	-0.55	-0.14	0.1

730

731 **Figure 1** Geographic locations of the 236 dryland sites surveyed and distribution of
 732 global desert biomes and drylands. The desert biomes under the Last Glacial
 733 Maximum (**a**) and current environmental conditions (**b**) were obtained from Ray &
 734 Adams (2001) and Olson et al. (2001), respectively. The current extent of drylands, as
 735 defined by the aridity index (AI, the ratio of precipitation to potential
 736 evapotranspiration), is shown in panel (**c**) (source: Trabucco & Zomer, 2009).
 737 Drylands include arid and hyper-arid ($AI < 0.2$), semi-arid ($0.2 \leq AI < 0.5$) and dry
 738 sub-humid ($0.5 \leq AI < 0.65$) regions.

739

740

741

742

743 **Figure 2** The unique and shared proportions of variations in multifunctionality
 744 explained by different predictors. We used variation partitioning analysis to calculate
 745 the proportions of variations. Significance levels are as follows: *** $P < 0.001$, ** $P <$
 746 0.01 . The significance of the shared variation could not be statistically tested. The
 747 unexplained residual variance was 0.49.

748

749

750

751

752

753

754

755

756

757

758

759

760 **Figure 3** Confirmatory path analysis (CPA) accounting for the direct and indirect
 761 effects of environmental predictors on multifunctionality. (a) The significant path
 762 coefficients, describing the strength and sign of the relationships among the variables,
 763 are shown adjacent to the arrows (significance levels as follows: $*** P < 0.001$, $** P$
 764 < 0.01 , $*P < 0.05$). Paths of site elevation and slope were not included for simplicity,
 765 since the main objective of this study was to evaluate the legacy effects of climate and
 766 biome. MAT: mean annual temperature; MAP: annual precipitation; Soil sand: soil
 767 sand content. The CPA conducted had a Fisher's C = 5.57, four degrees of freedom
 768 and a P -value = 0.23, suggesting that it had a good fit to our data (Grace, 2006). (b)
 769 Standardized total (direct + indirect) effects of desert and climate legacies, and of
 770 current desert and climate on multifunctionality, based on CPA.